

Comparative Evaluation of Student Approaches in Educational Sciences and Students' Relationships to Violence

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Abstract

School violence, when taken as a whole, is understood as a multifaceted structure that prevents growth and learning, causes negative changes in the school climate, and includes both students and teachers, even though the conceptualization of school violence by various researchers is distinct from one another (Furlong & Morrison, 2000). According to Harris (1990), traditional educational practices that contribute to the rise in violent behavior include the following: (i) teachers seeing themselves as the source of knowledge rather than producing knowledge together with students; (ii) teachers who encourage competition rather than cooperation among students; and (iii) students who directly accept knowledge rather than questioning it. (iv) They create their own norms for the classroom and ask students to adhere to these norms. (v) They employ authoritarian methods of classroom management rather than democratic methods. It has been shown that researchers may reap benefits by participating in straightforward preventative programs that aim to lower risk factors, boost protective variables, and address the issue of violence in schools. The purpose of these initiatives is to lessen the occurrence of violent acts in schools by decreasing risk factors and enhancing protective variables. The ability of students to recognize peer groups, the development of awareness of alternative behavioral norms, and the creation of a bond between the students participating in these trainings are the three primary reasons why researchers benefit from the implementation of prevention programs in this context. [C]ontextually situated prevention programs also allow students to develop awareness of alternative behavioral norms (Miller & Kraus , 2008). As an additional point of emphasis, the research that has been done in this area suggests that the professional responsibilities of school counselors in the 21st century should be rethought due to the importance of such preventative research.

Keywords: *Student Approaches in Educational Sciences, Violence Tendency of Students, Perception of Violence Psychologically, Violence in Education, Diversity of Perception of Violence in Education*

1. Introduction

One should give some thought to the issue of *violence in the classroom*. Researchers (Furlong et al., 2000) believe that in the 21st century, school counselors should try to reduce the risk factors that cause violence at school and increase student participation in school by implementing early screening and prevention programs. In addition, researchers believe that school counselors should try to reduce the risk factors that cause bullying at school. In addition, guidance counselors at schools should work toward increasing the percentage of students who earn their high school diplomas. D'Zurilla and Goldfried (1971) were the first to design the model to address social issues, and it was subsequently developed by D'Zurilla, Nezu, and Maydeu-Olivares. D'Zurilla and Goldfried (1971) were the first to design the model to address social issues. (D'Zurilla et al., 2002, 2004) It is the process of solving all the problems (personal, interpersonal, social, etc.) that an individual may encounter during his daily life in a conscious, rational, and purposeful manner.

2. Being able to resolve constructively through face-to-face negotiation

It has been observed that individuals believe they have the capacity to settle these issues in either a destructive manner by engaging in violent behavior or in a constructive manner by engaging in face-to-face dialogue. When looking at literature from throughout the world, researchers (Johnson & Johnson, 1995a) claim that differences of opinion are a normal and unavoidable aspect of everyday life. In addition, it can be shown that individuals express the belief that they may constructively address these disputes by bargaining face to face with one another. Because of this, schools must adopt an initiative-taking approach rather than placing their primary emphasis on the prevention of confrontations amongst pupils. Students should be instructed on how to address their differences constructively and amicably with one another, and new behavioral expectations should be established. Examining the relevant literature reveals that it has been our nation's goal since the beginning of the 2000s to avoid behaviors such as violence, hostility, and bullying at the primary, secondary, and high school levels; It is common knowledge that a great number of training programs geared toward enhancing problem-solving abilities have been adapted or developed, and their efficacy has been evaluated (Akgün & Araz, 2014; Bedel & Ar, 2011; Türnüklü, Kacmaz,

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&ki Conflict Solution, Akgün & Araz), 2014, Interpersonal Problem Solving Skills Training, Bedel and Ar 2011, First Step to Success Antisocial Behaviors Prevention Program In addition to these studies, it has been observed that training programs on peace and peacebuilding strategy have been developed, and their efficacy has been tested in recent years (Sadri - Dairchi & Bilge, 2014; Sakal, 2011; Sadkal, Türnüklü & Totan, 2012). These programs have been shown to be effective (Sadkal, Türnüklü & Totan, 2012). It has been shown that participating in these programs is beneficial (Sakal, 2011; Sadkal, Türnüklü, and Totan). The term "Peace education" refers to this kind of academic instruction. Students can gain the information, skills, attitudes, and values that are important for the development of amicable interactions as well as the peaceful and constructive settlement of problems. This is accomplished via education (Johnson & Johnson, 2006). When the relevant research is looked at, it is discovered that many different models of peace education are utilized in various countries of the globe. The geographical areas that are covered by each of these models, as well as the nature of the teachings that are taught, are distinct from one another (Reardon, 2000).

Researchers (Bar-Tall and Rosen, 2009; Harris, 2004) claim that it is normal for the content and scope of peace education to vary according to the socio-political structure of a society as well as the type of violence that is experienced in that society. Additionally, it is normal for the content and scope of peace education to change over time. It is common for there to be this kind of variety in substance and breadth. For instance, the primary focus of peace education programs in regions that are plagued by ethnic conflict is multiculturalism, along with the reduction of hostilities and the enhancement of empathy. On the other hand, the primary focus of peace education programs in regions that are dominated by peace is on global issues, human rights and freedoms, equality, and justice (Harris, 2010).

It is possible to say that the purpose of education for peace is to prevent all forms of violence on all levels, including the internal, interpersonal, intergroup, and international levels, and to acquire the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that will ensure peace. It is possible to say that the purpose of peace education is to realize this, even though the topics covered, and the scope of the programs offered to teach peace vary. 2003). Because of this, the primary objective of peace

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education in the context of the school setting should be to discourage aggressive behavior on the part of both students and faculty.

Work done by Z. Topcu Kabasakal, AS Sakal, and A. Türnüklü demonstrates that it is possible to cultivate one's existing set of abilities as well as their attitudes. Benbenishty and Astor (2005) provide a definition of school violence as acts that are conducted with the intention of causing physical or emotional harm to individuals who are a part of the school, as well as to their belongings and the property of the school. Henry (two thousand), on the other hand, defined violence in the school setting as the use of force by individuals, institutions, or social processes to repress or humiliate others. The following is Henry's definition of the term: With this concept, the researcher is not referring to acts of violence that involve only physical contact; rather, it places an emphasis on the psychological, economic, social, and moral aspects of acts of violence.

This method touches on a broad variety of subjects, including the following:

According to social problem-solving theory, it is believed that the skills required to solve social problems have a structure consisting of several dimensions. According to this theory, problem-solving orientation and problem-solving style are the two components that make up social problem-solving (D'Zurilla et al. 2002, 2004).

Both aspects can be considered separate from one another. Individuals who have a problem orientation have cognitive-emotional schemas that are quite stable and are representative of the tendency of the individual to find solutions to problems that they face in their day-to-day lives. The approach to solving problems that is referred to as the problem-solving style incorporates both cognitive and behavioral strategies for dealing with the challenges that an individual experiences in their everyday life. Research conducted in 2002 and 2004 by D'Zurilla et al. indicates that problem orientation can be broken down into two primary dimensions:

- *positive problem orientation and*
- *Negative problem orientation*

The tendency of an individual to view a problem as an opportunity, to believe that he can find a solution to the problem at hand, to have faith in his own capabilities, to try to cope with problems,

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and so on is known as positive problem orientation. The tendency of an individual to see a problem as a challenge that needs to be conquered is an example of orientation. Negative problem orientation is characterized by an individual's tendency to see real-life difficulties as a significant risk to himself, to believe that he cannot manage the situation, and to distrust his own abilities. This tendency can be seen because of an individual's tendency to view real-life difficulties as a potential threat. According to D'Zurilla et al. (2002) and 2004 research, there are three primary dimensions of approaches to problem solving: rational problem solving, careless-impulsive problem solving, and avoidant problem solving.

The individual applies a logical and methodical strategy to the resolution of the issues that arise in his everyday life according to the rational approach to problem solving; The individual takes the careless-impulsive approach by acting carelessly and impulsively with the first option that comes to mind, without considering too many solution options; the individual takes the avoidant approach by delaying the process of solving the problem or waiting for the problem to solve itself.

Therefore, according to the social problem-solving theory, the only problem-solving style that is functional is rational problem-solving; one can draw the conclusion that other problem-solving styles are not functional. Recent research (Ozdemir, Kuzucu, & Koruklu, 2013) has shown that participating in social problem solving can be an effective method of coping with adversity.

3. *Aggression (Özdemir et al., 2013).*
4. *Anxiety (Siu and Shek, 2010).*
5. *Life stress, loneliness, and suicide attempt (Hirsch, Chang & Jeglic, 2012).*
6. *Higher hope (Chang, 1998); self-esteem, life satisfaction (Hamarta, 2009).*
7. *Interpersonal relationships (Sumi, 2012); and family functionality (Siu & Shek, 2010).*
(“(PDF) Peace Education Program Students’ Violence Tendencies and ...” (“(PDF) Peace Education Program Students’ Violence Tendencies and ...”)

Program", which is suitable for the ninth-grade level and based on the themes of peacemaking and peacebuilding, was found to be effective in the resolution of conflicts among students. As a result of the findings of this study, the creation, implementation, and evaluation of the effectiveness of the program to prevent school violence, which is thought to influence the psychological adjustment

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processes of the students, is related to creating a package program that can be used by practitioners currently working in the sector. For this reason, a research has been conducted on how the peace education program affects students' tendencies towards violence and their ability to find peaceful solutions to social problems. The main hypothesis underlying the research is expressed as follows:

There is a significant difference between the control and placebo groups, respectively, in the linear composition of the violence tendency and social critical thinking skills posttest and follow-up test average scores of ninth grade students who participated in the peace education program .”

These ratings were changed based on the average results of a pre-test measuring violent tendencies and the ability to solve social problems.

3. What is Violence?

When a person engages in violent conduct, they are preventing their own mental, moral, and physical development, as well as their involvement in social life. When it comes to students, administrators, teachers, and other staff members, violence in the classroom refers to their antagonistic conduct. These interactions might be of a physical, psychological, or sexual character, and they can take place between students, among students, or even between students and students. The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that contribute to violence in schools and to place these factors in the wider context of individuals, families, and institutions. In addition, one of the subgoals of this study is to determine the factors that contribute to violence in schools. In addition to a wide range of other responsibilities, the school oversees delivering education and training to its students. Some of these responsibilities include making the school atmosphere more manageable, stable, and clean. The goal of cleaning at school is to establish a clean environment by removing pointless and hazardous elements from the existing one. This will allow for the creation of a clean atmosphere (Tezcan, 1994). Schools are forced to deal with a broad range of inappropriate student conduct for several reasons, which is an unfortunate situation.

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There is evidence that aggressive conduct among children and adolescents is infectious (Donat Bacolu & Ozdemir, 2012; Webster- Stratton, 1999), and there is evidence that some students are injured because of the spread of hostile behavior. Flannery et al. (2003) found that children and teens of school age are more prone to participate in bullying and other hostile actions than children of earlier ages. Gokler (2009) and şık (2009) assert that bullying among students is a significant barrier to the ability of schools to perform their duties as secure institutions. When children and adolescents are bullied or subjected to several types of violence, this may have a negative impact not just on their overall development but also on their mental health and wellbeing. When two individuals are familiar with one another, their relationship has the potential to deteriorate into tyranny, which is defined by ongoing and intense antagonism (Farrington , 1997).

The repeated and intentional use of physical force by one student or group against another student or group is the defining characteristic of the pattern of conduct known as bullying (Furniss , 2000). The dominating person's cruel and humiliating treatment of the submissive person creates an ongoing source of tension for the submissive person (Besag , 1989; Olweus , 1991; Roland, 1989; Smith, 1991). Recent studies have shown that bullying may be categorized as an aggressive conduct. At school, some examples of bullying conduct include naming victims, making fun of them, verbally threatening them, isolating them, humiliating them, and humiliating them more. According to Piskin (2002), some forms of bullying include the victim being threatened and then having their goods and money stolen. Briefly, the term "stiffness" refers to a behavior that is rigid and inflexible, and it is distinguished using physical force.

There have been several previous efforts to describe violence, but this one, which was developed by the World Health Organization, is the most thorough. This definition of violence states that it is "the use of physical force or threats against oneself, another person, a particular community or group, which may result in injury, death, physical harm, certain developmental disorders, or deprivation." Another definition of violence states that it is "the use of physical force or threats against a particular community or group." The definition of violence provided by the American Psychological Association served as the inspiration for this one (Krug et al., 2002). The phrase "violence at school" refers to illegal actions and aggressive conduct that disrupts development and learning while also causing damage to the environment of the school (Furlong & Morrison, 2000).

It is imperative that precautions be made to prevent reaching this stalemate, since it may result in issues in a variety of settings. It is of the utmost importance to address the issue of bullying and violence in schools, as it has a negative impact on a person's pursuit of education, mental health, and overall development. Several studies have concluded that the prevention of violence in schools cannot be accomplished solely through the application of strategies such as the presence of police officers, legislation, and disciplinary sanctions. According to Perry (2001), children who are more likely to engage in aggressive behavior are those whose families are rude at school, do not participate in social activities or stay out of these, have problems, and fail in their lessons, they are victims of or witness violence at home, or they are abused. Other risk factors include Children who come from families that behave well have a lower risk of being abused and their families being dismantled.

4. Bullying and Violence at School

People who live in the area in which the school is situated are members of the community that is part of the school. Because it is a social setting, the school has students and staff who are also inhabitants of the surrounding community. Naturally, the individuals who make up the school community bring the traits of the culture they came from to the school. Additionally, they bring the behaviors that they acquired outside of school with them to school with them. Depending on how you look at it, these activities may be beneficial, or they may be detrimental. Bullying occurs in schools when younger or physically weaker students are harassed, tortured, or harassed at school by older or physically stronger students. When younger or physically weaker students are bullied at school by older or physically stronger students, this behavior is called school bullying. Student violence may be defined by acts such as beating, slapping, shoving, pulling, frightening, ridiculing, angering, naming, and humiliating other students at school, according to this definition of the word (Pişkin, 2002). Individual acts of violence are also a possibility, as is the case when groups of students who have similar personality characteristics decide to establish gangs. Gangs may also be formed by students who share similar interests. If steps are not done to prevent this situation from occurring, the young people involved may find that it gives them power, that they love it, or that

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they think that other people deserve it (Tural, 2006). This strategy may be used to promote unwanted and bad behaviors, and similar tactics can be employed not just in the classroom but also outside of the classroom. As the frequency of violent actions perpetrated in schools continues to rise, people no longer see these establishments as locations where instructional activities may take place in an environment free from danger (MEB, 2015).

According to Kazmaz (2006), violent acts may take place in schools between students and teachers, as well as between students and school administrators and personnel. According to Güçlü (two thousand), the role of the principal at the school is that of the person in charge of administrative matters. Because of this, the functions and duties of school administrators are critical in the fight against aggression and bullying in educational institutions. Academic research on the topic did not start anywhere in the globe until the early 1970s, even though bullying in schools is a very widespread occurrence (Olweus, 1995). In the 1980s and early 1990s, it started to get the attention of countries like the United States of America, Canada, Australia, Britain, and the Netherlands. There are studies which state that the topic is treated as a study field, which demonstrates that the problem of bullying and violence in the school setting is also a concern in Turkey (Avc, 2006). It is possible to say that most of the studies on the topic focus on the issue of bullying (Karaman - Kepenekci, 2003; Kapc, 2004; Pişkin, 2002), and it is also possible to say that most of the research that were conducted on the topic focused on the issue of bullying. It is unacceptable for there to be violence in classrooms (Aksu, 2002).

On the other hand, there has been a rise in the number of instances of violence that have taken place in schools over the course of the past few years. Because of this, more attention has been paid to the problem, and more efforts have been made to find ways to avoid and lessen the amount of violence that occurs in schools. According to osk (2004), the number of people working to eliminate bullying and other forms of violence in schools has increased. It is reasonable to assume that these activities will contribute to the reduction of instances of bullying and violence in educational settings.

5. Causes of Bullying and Other Violence in Schools and Prevention Methods

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The administration of the school should take the necessary precautions to ensure the safety of the school's premises, both inside and out, work to reduce the number of circumstances that could result in acts of violence, aggression, or bullying at the school, educate the faculty and staff about the problem at hand, convene meetings to discuss the matter, identify the students who are the source of the issues, and make certain that these students receive treatment without undue delay. originates. In addition, it is of the utmost importance that the administration of the schoolwork to reduce the likelihood of occurrences such as violence, aggression, and aggression, as well as to increase the interaction between schools and schools, and to ensure that children receive both social and educational assistance. Because of the negative effects that these issues have on students, research that aims to reduce bullying and violence in schools is of even greater importance now than it was before.

Rigidity, conduct that is stiff and inflexible, and the use of raw force are all aspects that may be used to provide a concise definition of the word "violence." Incidents of violence may take the form of a wide variety of various kinds of behaviors and acts that are intended to intimidate and threaten other people. Violence is defined as "the infliction of damage, death, or bodily harm to oneself, another person, a specific community or group, as well as certain developmental problems or deprivation" (Krug) et al. 2002: 5). This definition comes from the World Health Organization. According to this interpretation, violent conduct may be classified as activity whether it entails physical contact. In other words, violent behavior can be both overt and covert. The incidence of violence may be dealt with in a variety of diverse ways since it is seen in a variety of diverse ways. Psychological violence may be defined as any attitude or conduct that has a detrimental impact on the mental health of the person, causes the individual to experience anguish, and gives the individual the impression that they are being put under pressure. Any attitude or action that is aimed towards one's moral principles and poses a danger to one's moral lifestyle is referred to as "spiritual violence," and the phrase may be used interchangeably with "physical violence." When a person is prohibited from exercising their rights under the law or when the law is construed against the individual in a manner that conflicts with the norms of international law, this is an example of the kind of legal violence known as "legal violence."

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Criminalizing economic conduct and preventing other individuals from receiving financial assistance are both aspects of economic oppression that may be seen as forms of economic violence. The difference between a restricted definition of violence and a wide definition of violence is yet another distinction that may be stated about violence.

Acts of physical assault are included in the conventional conception of what constitutes violence. On the other hand, physical violence is an act that is heavy and painful that is perpetrated by a third party against the bodily integrity of the person and is directed from the outside to the interior of the body. This kind of violence is often covert and difficult to identify when it occurs. A key problem is the way violent conduct is depicted and condoned in the workplace as well as in daily life. The acceptance or condoning of violent conduct by victims changes the nature of the activity from one that is perceived to be violent to one that is seen to be a pattern of behavior. Most significantly, if people accept violent conduct as a regular part of life, then this is not seen as a problem since it is thought to be the usual.

1.7% of all deaths that occur between the ages of 15 and 59 can be attributed to violence, as determined by the findings of the research on the National Burden of Disease that was conducted by the Turkish Ministry of Health. More than 2,900 persons lost their lives as a direct consequence of acts of violence in 2006, as shown by figures produced by the General Directorate of Security. [Citation needed] According to the findings of the same sources, there were 321.676 breaches of public order committed against individuals in the year 2006. The following are some of the factors that can lead to aggressive behavior in children:

- a. *The mother's lack of access to antenatal care and the conditions given by birth causes her to be born ill. Brain damage can result from problems during pregnancy or during childbirth; as a result, these individuals may be more likely to experience violent behavior in their lifetime or to engage in violent behavior themselves.*
- b. *Being an unwanted child in terms of gender, number of children, and timing not only increases the child's likelihood of being exposed to physical violence, but also causes the child's personality to develop, leading to aggressive behavior. When a person sees his or her mental health as poor, they are at risk of committing*

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aggressive and violent acts. Hyperactivity and impulsivity, melancholy, poor self-esteem, and anxiety are common in those who engage in violent behavior.

Children who have difficulties with their mental health are at a greater risk of engaging in violent behavior. Children and teenagers who are having difficulties at school have a greater risk of being exposed to potentially violent situations and, therefore, are more likely to engage in aggressive behavior.

- c. Children and youth who do not attend school are more likely to be in violent environments and engage in violent behavior. Being in a violent environment and being exposed to violence before causes children and young people to engage in violent behavior.*
- d. When young people are exposed to violent situations, they may not know how to deal with these behaviors, and it may be difficult for them to find solutions to their difficulties without resorting to violence. Young people's information was collected on a variety of topics, such as their ability to make choices in challenging conditions, their ability to say "no", their ability to cope with stress, and their reaction when they do something they did not do. When you want to do it or when there is a problem. It has been discovered that today's children, who give importance to the use of non-violent communication strategies rather than aggressive actions, are not enough in critical thinking skills.*
- e. It is seen that the cultural structure of the family is effective in the frequency of violent behavior. (For example, violent behavior is more common in homes where the use of violence is normalized and used for teaching and solving problems.)*
- f. It has been shown that violence behaviors increase in children and youth. Adults, on the other hand, are caused by factors such as inability to adapt to urban life and changes in the social and economic structure of families settled in the city. In addition to these: factors such as excessive drinking and drug use, domestic stress,*
- g. The feeling of social exclusion and isolation from the society experienced by the family.*
- h. An individual with a family history of mental illness or behavioral problems.*

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- i. *Family members who become parents at an early age do not have sufficient life experience,*
- j. *While domestic discipline should be used as a positive method in raising the child, ignorance of discipline methods or the use of violence as a discipline method,*
- k. *Violent behavior in children because of parental behavior turning into a lack of self-confidence and family conflicts,*
- l. *Those who experienced domestic violence as children are more likely to engage in violent behavior in their adulthood. One of the reasons that expose or encourage violence is the increasing level of violence perpetrated by adults.*

Students who dislike school and have a low level of commitment to their education are more likely to commit crimes than students who like their education and are committed to it. This conclusion is based on several studies that were conducted in developed western nations to decide the nature of the connection that exists between involvement in school and participation in activities related to school and the commission of crimes.

6. Widespread Public Opinion That Schools Aren't Safe Environments for Children

The growing attention paid by the media to acts of violence that take place in schools all over the world has had a significant impact on the prevalent view that schools are not secure environments for children. Numerous studies have been conducted at the national level in several European countries, the United States of America, and Canada; all these studies have consistently found high rates of children reporting being bullied or being bullied themselves. It is believed that around 200,000 firearms are taken into schools throughout the United States daily. This claim is given more weight by the fact that a student is killed by gunfire every half hour, which is just one example of a statistic that supports it. It is common knowledge that countries in other parts of the world are contending with the same issues. According to Alex Molnar and Barbara Lindquist (1995: 50), the prevalence of violent behavior in the United States is contributed to by several factors, including the following:

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1. *Poverty*
2. *Isolation from the surrounding family environment*
3. *child maltreatment*
4. *culture of violence*
5. *materialistic culture*
6. *It is a tyranny and at the same time unhealthy competition.*

Most states in the United States have begun to implement specialized programs to combat the issue of violence in educational environments. For instance, in the city of Chicago, over 120 police officers are delegated to work in the city's various educational institutions. Additionally, there is a team of parent volunteers working in each school.

Other actions taken at these schools are detailed in the following list:

1. *There are 24-hour security cameras in the corridors and cafeteria (There has been a significant reduction in gang fights thanks to these cameras).*
2. *Character education programs where honesty, dedication, and other high-minded ideals are discussed and debated.*
3. *Bargaining with contemporaries (students of the same age try to resolve their disagreements through dialogue).*
4. *"learning centres" ready to solve small problems before they turn into bigger challenges.*
5. *Special education classes for male students in mixed-gender groups run by male educators and law enforcement (possibly because of more violence by men than women).*
6. *Young people are given the opportunity to take part in programs and activities designed to teach them to respect themselves and others as well as to be proud of their heritage and culture (Alkan 1998, Köseolu and Soran (2004) and Çepni (2005)). Modern technology, computer or electronic tools, materials produced by the combination of ideas and talents, making life easier or a matter of address...*

The use of technology helps to bridge the gap between the challenges faced by practitioners and the research and theoretical interpretations that try to explain those challenges. In the field of education, one could make the case that technology, which has left its imprint on our era, helps

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bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and educational practices. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] According to Alkan (1997) and Ileri (1988), the purpose of educational technology is "to increase the functionality of these processes by using the knowledge and skills that will facilitate education and learning." Educational technology also aims "to increase the functionality of these processes by using the knowledge and skills that will facilitate education and learning." Ileri (1988) states that the purpose of the development of educational technology was "to increase the functionality of these processes by using the knowledge and skills that will facilitate education and learning." "The relevance of the behavioral sciences can be attributed to their reliance on data on human and non-human resources, as well as communication and learning."

Helping people achieve their educational goals, both in terms of results and means, is the subject of extensive research and evaluation (Uşun 2000, man 2005, Ozmen 2005). Modern methods and procedures are expertly used. These researchers were investigating various aspects of the concept of educational technology. It is not the goal of teaching students in the sciences about science and technology to cram information into their heads; rather, the aim is to instill in them the scientific worldview and problem-solving abilities that will prepare them for their future careers. To phrase it another way, the aim is to "raise people who research and think about the events they encounter in daily life in a cause-effect relationship and establish logical connections between the events" (epni, Küclik, and Ayvac 2003).

education in the sciences; This type of education is direct and firsthand and depends on the student's interests and needs, level of development, etc. Chepni (2005)

Knowledge and comprehension are the most important goals of scientific education, followed by research and discovery, creative thinking and output, emotional understanding and appreciation, practical application, and usage (MEB 2004). According to Enpolat (2005), pupils who have difficulty understanding scientific ideas tend to form preconceptions, which in turn inhibits their capacity to learn about science. [Citation needed] Concepts should be taught to students by providing them with a variety of active strategies and scientific facts (Rothkopf 1995; Sarh 2002; Akcay 2002). These strategies and facts will both capture students' attention and hold it (Rothkopf

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1995; Sarh 2002; Akcay 2002). According to Isman (2005), the definition of a computer is "a set of systems that maintains information on topics, processes this information according to certain fundamental principles, and draws the outcomes of completed operations." [Citation needed] According to Akcay (2002), the use of a computer is an easy and effective way to supply the student with a variety of attention and concentration aids such as music, different characters, colors, and animations. These aids may be sent to the student in an uncomplicated manner.

In the 1960s, industrialized nations started to launch research and development projects aimed at integrating computers into educational settings. These initiatives were mostly focused on elementary and secondary schools. Many different computer programs in the academic subjects of mathematics, physics, and science have been evaluated as part of the educational initiatives conducted at universities. These programs were evaluated within the context of the educational initiatives conducted (Meyveci 1997).

In 1981, just 18% of schools in the United States had at least one computer that was used for instructional purposes. By 1995, however, that number had climbed to 99% of schools. With the introduction of computers into secondary school institutions in 1984, the Ministry of National Education began doing research on computer education to better understand how to best instruct students. The Ministry of National Education was the one responsible for conducting these studies. In later years, studies referred to as "Computer Aided Education" were started, particularly at the secondary school level (Uşun 2000). According to Seniş (1993), the use of technology is the last level that is reached in deciding answers to the issues that exist inside the educational system. As a result, the benefits of incorporating computers into educational settings are discussed along with the reasons against doing so. For instance, pedagogical reality argues that computers will enrich learning, while professional reality suggests that children should be prepared to use technology in a technological society, and social reality suggests that students should be prepared for society by being equipped with modern technologies (Akkoyunlu 1993).). Social reality also suggests that students be prepared for society by being equipped with modern technologies (Akkoyunlu 1993).).

For instance, study conducted in the United States showed that eighty percent of teachers had been exposed to at least one of eleven distinct forms of violent behavior in schools either during the

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current school year or the previous school year. The survey was conducted in every single region of the nation (McMahon et al., 2014). The results of the International Teaching and Learning Survey (TALIS, 2013) show that the United States of America is the nation that has the greatest incidence of violent incidents in its educational institutions. The percentage of principals who report that their teachers have experienced any form of violence by students, such as intimidation or verbal abuse, is close to 14%, which is higher than the 10% average that is reported internationally. According to the findings of another study, the percentage of teachers who had been victimized varied from state to state, and more specifically, the percentage of teachers who had been threatened with physical violence varied from state to say as well; the rate reached as high as 17% in some states. According to the findings of another study, the rate at which students are victimized by teachers varies significantly from state to state.

Violence in schools is linked to turnover and turnover among teaching staff, as well as a range of other detrimental effects, such as negative effects on teachers' mental health, according to an ever-expanding body of research coming from a variety of developed and developing countries. This research finds that violence in schools is linked to turnover and turnover among teaching staff. However, the prevalence of violence in schools and the ways in which it influences the degree to which teachers are dedicated to their work varies from nation to nation. Researchers have issued a warning that paying an excessive amount of attention to research that is conducted within a nation can led to narrow-mindedness, which has the potential to lead to various educational practices that are not sensitive to the context of the situation. The purpose of this research is to contribute to the development of theories, policies, and intervention strategies that can lessen the toll that school violence takes on educators in a variety of countries. The countries of Mexico, the United States of America, the United Kingdom, and South Korea (also known as the Republic of Korea) have been chosen to take part in this research. The four countries, which are spread across three continents, are distinct from one another in a variety of respects, including their geographical characteristics, economic indicators, cultural characteristics, and educational systems. Because the United States is the location where most of the earlier research on school violence and teacher professional involvement has been conducted, the results of that research have been incorporated into this study as a context of the results. Because the educational and sociocultural systems in the

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United States and England are quite comparable, England was chosen as the country to evaluate whether the results in the United States could be replicated in a completely new sample of teachers from England. This was done because the educational and sociocultural systems in the United States and England are quite similar. The geographical and sociological characteristics of East Asia were given the utmost consideration when selecting South Korea as the region's representative. Additionally, Mexico was selected by Etevez and others (2016) to be the Latin American setting. This decision was made. This investigation was motivated by three research questions, which are as follows:

3. *How does the prevalence of school violence in the United States, United Kingdom, South Korea, and Mexico affect the level of professional involvement proved by educators in these countries?*
4. *How does the level of teacher self-efficacy affect the consequences of school violence on the level of professional commitment felt by teachers in each of the four countries?*
5. *Do stakeholder engagement and positive connections between teachers and students help prevent violence in schools?*

6. Conclusion

According to the findings of many pieces of research, violence in the classroom is a pervasive issue in K–12 public school settings, and it is associated with several serious and harmful effects on the educator. a dedication to teaching on the part of teachers (eg, work-related stress and burnout, decreased teaching effectiveness, withdrawal from teaching, and dismissal; Ingersoll , 2001; Pas et al., 2010; Martinez et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2015). Indeed, a lack of safety can inhibit a teacher's ability to "perform properly" (Schaufeli et al., 2002, page 73), which can result in a worsening of the professional disinterest that teachers feel in their jobs.

The perspectives of educators on the prevalence of violence in the classroom have the potential to have a significant impact on the overall quality of the educational system. These repercussions can influence the standard and consistency of the education that children receive in a variety of ways,

including the way teachers instruct, the rates of absenteeism, and the relationships that teachers have with their students. Other researchers have discovered that teachers who experience feelings of insecurity at school because of the possibility of violence have lower levels of job satisfaction (Williams et al., 1989), tend to be unmotivated and less committed to their work (Van Ginkel, 1987; Vettenburg, 2002), and even completely dismiss the profession. This encourages them to leave the teaching profession. Williams et al. found that teachers who reported feeling insecure at school due to the possibility of violence had lower levels of job satisfaction than their counterparts who did not report feeling insecure. Even though school administrators have a greater number of responsibilities, there is a lack of research in the existing literature on this topic.

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